

Determinism and Bias in Information for Fermions and Bosons?

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Information theory, which applies to compressing messages, suggests that $\ln(\text{probability})$ is information. Shannon's entropy is -1 times the average information i.e. $-\sum_i P(i)\ln(P(i))$. For a classical gas in the canonical approximation, this is of the form of an average conserved quantity e.g. $E_{\text{ave}} = \sum_i e_i P(e_i)$.

In deterministic classical mechanics one may characterize an elastic two body collision by $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. In a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas these same deterministic reactions occur, but there is also a static probability $P(e_i)$. The question seems to be whether $P(e_i)$ brings any new "physical" information into a scattering reaction. One already knows that a particle contributes energy e_i . Is there something else brought in? If the answer is no, then using the product of probabilities $P(e_1)P(e_2)$ and taking \ln leads to $\ln(P(e_1)) + \ln(P(e_2))$ suggests that $\ln(P(e_1)) = A(e_1 - B)$ where A and B are constant. Thus information considerations link probability $P(e_i)$ to a deterministic quantity e_i . One does not have to consider reaction balance or the maximization of entropy subject to a constraint. One simply finds the appropriate probability $P_{\text{appropriate}}(e_1)$ which describes an overall change to the state e_1 . For the MB case, $P_{\text{appropriate}}(e_i) = P(e_i)$ (MB) which gives a static description of the number of particles with e_i .

In other cases, however, there may be bias. Consider quantum scattering of fermions or bosons. If the collisions are elastic, one again has the classical deterministic $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ expression. There is also a static $P(e_i)$ (Fermi-Dirac) for fermions and $P(e_i)$ Bose-Einstein for bosons. One is, however, interested in collisions which create and maintain the equilibrium situation. If there is bias in these collisions, then $P_{\text{appropriate}}(e_i)$ may differ from $P(e_i)$. The information e_1 is the full contribution of particle 1 to the collision. Thus one also needs a full probability describing probability movement out of state e_1 . $P(e_1)$ is proportional only to the probability flow out of e_1 due to scattering, but there is a "bias" factor namely $1 - P(e_1)$ which prevents another particle from entering state e_1 . This biases a reaction. As a result $P_{\text{appropriate}}(e_1) = P(e_1) / (1 - P(e_1))$ for a fermion. This may be seen from a reaction balance equation: $P(e_1)(1 - P(e_3)) P(e_2)(1 - P(e_4)) = P(e_3)(1 - P(e_1))P(e_4)(1 - P(e_2))$ for fermions. For bosons there is an enhancement. One may obtain product probabilities by forming $P(e_i)/(1 - P(e_i))$. This is the full contribution in terms of probabilities of particle i to a collision and so its \ln should equal $A(e - B)_i$ which is its full information contribution to the reaction. If the two are not equal, it means there is more information (excluding parameters such as T temperature and μ the chemical potential) than e_i in the problem.

Information Theory

Information theory deals with messages which contain letters which appear with different probabilities. It is concerned with ways to compress such a message. Information is defined as $\ln(P(i))$ where $P(i)$ is the probability for letter i to appear. Shannon's entropy is given as $-\sum_i P(i)\ln(P(i))$. This is the average of $\ln(P(i))$ i.e. of information and is analogous to an average in a canonical system for example average energy of a gas:

$$E_{ave} = \sum_i P(e_i) e_i \quad ((1))$$

As a result, one may consider $\ln(P(i))$ as a kind of substance which is contributed to a “collision” of letters. Now letters do not scatter, but a collision may be thought of as an interchange of two letters with probabilities $P(1)P(2)$ with two other letters such that $P(3)P(4)=P(1)P(2)$. In such a way information is a conserved quantity and each letter contributes $\ln(P(i))$ to a “collision”. This leaves the content of the message unchanged (because one ignores ordering).

This scenario is identical to a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. Each gas particle may appear with probability $P(e_i)$, but it is e_i which is the contribution to an elastic collision, thus $\ln(P(e_i))=e_i$. One does not need to consider maximizing Shannon’s entropy = $-\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i P(e_i)$. Neither does one need reaction balance. Collisions occur and each of these is deterministic i.e. is elastic and characterized by e_i from each particle. The fact that one has probabilities does not bring any new information into the scenario. Thus given that $P(e_i)$ exists, it or a function of it if there is bias, must yield the information e_i which is the only information contributed. Given that AND situations are related to probability products, \ln converts a product to a sum and so $\ln(P(e_i))$ is information. This should suffice in yielding the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

One may note that this argument essentially links probability $P(e_i)$ to a classical deterministic value e_i which is called information (if you will). Given that e_i is essential to collisions and is the full contribution of particle i to such a collision, one needs to ensure that one uses an appropriate probability. In other words $P(e_i)$ might not be the only probability in the picture and it might not be the correct one to use if there is bias.

Bias and Fermions and Bosons

Given that interactions based on “physics” create and maintain equilibrium, it is essential that these reactions are understood. In information theory where a message is created with each letter having a probability $P(i)$ or one rolls a die or flips a coin, one only needs one set of probabilities. For the case of fermions or bosons, each particle is characterized by an energy e_i (its information which is contributed to a collision). Furthermore, there is a $P(e_i)$ value for fermions and a different one for bosons in a gas in equilibrium. The question is whether $P(e_i)$ describes the full probability contribution to an interaction. In other words is it the case that if you have a particle with e_i it may simply scatter such that $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ with no other physical considerations? For fermions and bosons the answer is no. Each particle contributes e_i to a collision, but the probability contribution is more complicated. Thus $\ln(P(e_i))$ is not equal to e_i .

To see what probability contribution is made, one may write a reaction balance equation in order to see the “bias” in the reaction.

$$P(e_1)(1-/P(e_3)) P(e_2)(1-/P(e_4)) = P(e_3)(1-/P(e_1)) P(e_4)(1-/P(e_2)) \quad ((2))$$

- For fermions + for bosons

As a result, the overall probability object describe a particle with e_i is:

$$P(e_i) / [1 \mp P(e_i)] \quad (3)$$

If e_i is the full information carried by a particle into a reaction then \ln of (3) must be equal to this value with some adjustments i.e.

E_i may be written more generally as: $(e_i - u)/T$ where u is the chemical potential and T temperature i.e. both are constants.

The reason that \ln is needed is that probabilities multiply in an AND situation and one wants addition for conservation. In other words one has a deterministic elastic reaction such that e_i is the only information brought into a reaction, but quantum behaviour introduces bias (which may be described as a function of $P(e_i)$) into the scattering reaction and so $P(e_i)$ does not give a full description of a reaction. E_i is the full information and so must be matched with the \ln of a full probability expression.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that information theory which is involved in sending compressed messages which contains letters which appear with probabilities $P(i)$ uses a quantity called Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ where $\ln(P(i))$ is called information. In such a case this is of the form of a canonical average of $\ln(P(e_i))$ in analogy to $E_{ave} = \sum_i P(e_i) e_i$ for a canonical treatment of an ideal gas. As a result, given a message, one may consider collisions of letters i.e. the interchange of 1 and 2 with 3 and 4 such that $P(1)P(2) = P(3)P(4)$. This does not change the overall probability of the message, nor does it change the average of information $\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. In other words $\ln(P(i))$ appears as a conserved quantity in letter interchanges. For an MB gas, one has classical deterministic elastic collisions such that $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. One also has probabilities $P(e_i)$. The question is whether $P(e_i)$ brings any extra information to a collision. The answer is that it does not seem to. Thus $P(e_i)$ is the probability contribution to a collision and given that AND situations means multiplication of probabilities one needs \ln to convert this into a sum i.e. $\ln(P(e_1)) + \ln(P(e_2))$. Given that there is no new information, one must identify $\ln(P(e_i))$ with $A(e_i - B)$ where A and B are constants. ($A = 1/T$ and $B = 0$).

It is possible that there is physical bias in a collision as in the case of many fermions or many bosons. For fermions, no two identical fermions may occupy the same state and for bosons, there is an enhancement for scattering to occur in a state with many particles. As a result, $P(e_i)$ exists, but it is not the full contribution of probability to a collision. Using reaction balance, one may find that: $P(e_i) / [1 \mp P(e_i)]$ (- fermion, + boson) is the full expression based on e_i linked to a reaction. If this does not contribute any extra information beyond e_i then \ln of this value should be equal to $A(e_i - B)$ where $A = 1/T$ and $B = u$ the chemical potential.

